
Politics of Identity and Marginality: A Study of the Wancho Naga in Assam

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ABSTRACT

The politics of ethnic identity is not an uncommon phenomenon in a multi ethnic state like Assam. It has often intensified ethnic based protest, movement and conflicts. The identity politics has also prompted state interventions through various institutional arrangements i.e. autonomous state, districts and councils and developmental policies on ethnic lines. However, it has also been observed that these macro-level approaches often overlooked the precarious situation of various marginal or micro-ethnic groups. This study focuses on the Wancho Naga community settled in Charaideo district of Assam with a population of merely two to three thousand. Thus, the marginalized tribe like Wancho community faces an extreme identity crisis and continued to exclude from targeted governmental developmental policies and schemes. Against this backdrop, the present papers traces the historical presence and identity of the community, analyzes the factors of their identity crisis and understand the role of community organizations which negotiates their survival and identity in the socio-political realm of Assam. The study is based on both primary and secondary sources of data. The Primary data was gathered through ethnographic observation, focused group discussions and in-depth interviews with community members. Secondary data was sourced from books, academic journals, pamphlets and newspapers. The study offers a critical understanding of the challenges faced by micro-ethnic

groups in Assam and contributes to the broader discourse on identity politics and conflict resolution.

Introduction:

The contemporary politics of Assam has been characterized by the politics of ethnicity. Assam has experienced of ethnic assertion, conflicts and movement in both colonial and post colonial era. It has been observed that every ethnic group is conscious of its distinct identity and strives to protect, promote and preserve it at any cost and demand ethnic base institutional arrangement and developmental packages. According to Nathan Glazer and Daniel Moynihan the ethnicity is not simply a mix of affective sentiments, but like class and nationality it is also a means of political mobilization for advancing group interests. Ethnic groups are also interest groups. Orlando Patterson asserted that “The strength, scope, viability, and bases of ethnic identity are determined by, and are used to serve, the economic and general class interests of individuals.” Hence, interests are the sole determinant of ethnic identity and ethnic affiliation tends to be transient and situational as the benefits of ethnicity shift. Daniel Bell stated that “Ethnicity has become more salient because it can combine an interest with an affective tie. Cohen also suggested that cultural homogeneity of people facilitates their effective organization as an interest of group and boosts ethnic solidarity and identity.

In Assam, several major ethnic groups such as Bodo, Mishing, Karbi, Dimasa etc. have started demand for separate autonomous state, district and council on ethnic line. It has been found that this has often intensified conflicting situations in the state and the state has also often interfered with adoption of institutional arrangements and developmental packages for several ethnic groups. However, these macro level approaches often overlooked the precarious situation of micro ethnic groups like Wancho Naga living in Assam.

It is evident that the Wancho tribe is primarily residing in the Longding and the Tirap district of Arunachal Pradesh, the Mon district of Nagaland, the Sivasagar, Charaideo and the Dibrugarh districts of Assam as well as the Sagaiang and Kachin regions of Myanmar Bsurma. According to census report (2001), total Wancho population is 56,953 in Arunachal Pradesh only. The Wancho Naga people are also permanently living in 4 villages in Charaideo and Dibrugarh districts of Assam since time immemorial. The Wancho Naga settled in the Mon district of Nagaland is generally considered as Konyak Naga. However, it is observed that as compared to the same community living in other states of India’s northeastern region, the Wancho Naga living in Assam have been facing extreme ethnic identity crisis

due to due to limited political representation, socio-economic backwardness, lack of population strength, lack of institutional support and recognition, influence by the dominant culture etc. Against this backdrop, the present study has made an attempt to trace the historical identity of the Wancho Naga community, understand the factors of their identity crisis and the role of the community organizations which negotiates their survival and identity in the socio-political realm of Assam. The study offers a critical understanding of the challenges faced by micro-ethnic groups in Assam and contributes to the broader discourse on identity politics and conflict resolution as well.

Historical Presence and Identity of the Wancho Naga in Assam:

The Origin of the Term Wancho:

The term Wancho is the combination of *WAN* and *CHO*. The *WAN* have dual meanings. Firstly, it is the short form of *Zangwannu*, the main worship object of Wanchos. Secondly, *CHO* means to serve or to Acho-alit (worship). Therefore Wancho people are the worshiper and follower of Zangwannu (Almighty God). The Wancho also could be interpreted as Wancho which means ember, flame and torch etc. Behind this, theory is a myth that during the dispersion of races known as Mixfan-Mixjan (Mass Exodus) Wanchos as large group marched out with ember or fire. This Mixfan-Mixjan took place from the place of the Ofan-Tinu and divided into smaller groups in search of a suitable land for permanent settlement. Before they depart to another new territory, they challenged one another that the group which make fire and let the smoke goes up above the hills first shall be counted as the elder village. In this way, whenever, they occupy land, first of all they make big fire so that the smoke goes high up above the hills to signify their occupation of that particular territory. Whenever, they saw such smoke or fire of another group, they shouted at one another saying ‘Wunchua to hulax’ (Look at the fire). So, it might also be possible that the word Wancho derives from the word Wunchua.

Settlement pattern and State System from Pre-colonial to Modern Times:

The Wancho tribe is one of the major Naga tribes predominantly living in Longding, Tirap and Changlang district in Arunachal Pradesh, Mon district of Nagaland, Sibsagarh, Charaideo and Dibrugarh district of Assam and Kachin and Sagaing region of Myanmar Burma. According to census report (2001), they have the population of 56,953 in Arunachal Pradesh only. Basically, the Wancho people are divided into two major sections viz- *Tangkainusa and Sangkainusa*. The villages viz- *Pomhchao, Konyu, Kanyu, Gakkah and Ninu* are the leading villages of former section. The main villages of *Sanghainusa* viz- *Pumao, Nyanu, Chanu, Zunu, Chopnu, Senyua, Sangnyu* provided them with their local chief and

they occupied the lower belt of Wancho land. It is said that the *Tangkainusa* and *Sangkainusa* people are the first people to occupy this beautiful fertile land of present with unique geographical location in between mountainous range of Patkai and the plains of Assam.

In *Ahom* history it is clearly mentioned that during thirteen century when the *Ahoms* first moved across Patkai ranges, they were confronted by the Nagas, now known as Nocte, Tangsa, Wancho, and Konyak. The Wanchos were also termed as *Banfera*, *Khulun or Khuluniya* and also *Tablungias Nagas* by the *Ahoms* on the basis of their inhabited areas. Different tribes including the Wanchos living in the Patakai hills were also referred as Eastern Naga viz. Nagas of Sibsagar, *Boree Nagas* (friendly), *Abori Nagas* (Unfriendly), Patkai Nagas etc. by the British. It was during the thirteen century that the Nagas living on the slope of the Patkai hills termed by the British as Eastern Nagas i.e. Tangsas, Noctes, Lajus, Tutsa and Wanchos of Tirap and Changlang district of present Arunachal Pradesh and lower Konyak of Mon district of Nagaland, were the first come into contact with Ahoms.

It is observed that because of the modern state system, the Wancho inhabited areas split-up in different states i.e. Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Nagaland and Myanmar Burma. The North-East Frontier Agency (NEFA) was formed in 1951 by consolidating the areas of Kameng Frontier Division, Subansiri Frontier Division, Siang Frontier Division, Lohit Division Frontier, Tirap Frontier Division and Tuensang Frontier Division. In 1957, the Tuensang Frontier Division was separated from NEFA and formed Union Territory known as Naga Hills Tuensang Area (NHTA). With the 27th Constitutional Amendment Act, 1971, NEFA has been recommended as a Union Territory along with Mizoram and Meghalaya. The NEFA attained full-fledged statehood in 1986 and Wancho, Tangsa, Nokte Nagas were referred as ‘Any Naga Tribe’ and grouped in Tirap and Changlang districts.

It is also evident that as per the demands of peoples of these regions, the Parliament amended and enacted the Constitution (Schedule Tribes) Order (Amendment) Act, 2020 for revision in list of Scheduled Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh which recognized the Nokte, Tangsa, Tutsa and Wancho as distinct tribe in lieu of ‘Any Naga Tribes’ in serial No. 10 in list of Scheduled Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh. The Wanchos who are inhabited in Mon district of Nagaland are called as Konyak Naga and the Wanchos who are settled in some parts of Tirap district are recognized as Nocte. However, the Wancho tribe living in Assam is as still recognized as ‘Any Naga Tribe’.

The tradition of taxation system:

It is observed that taxation system was there between hilly Wancho and plains peoples that existed even up to mid 1960s. Later on, this taxation system was not practiced strictly and the plains people had also refused to pay this traditional taxation imposed by the hilly Wancho Rajas. Various forms of tax or collection pulled by the then chiefs of hilly Wancho are as discussed below.

It has been narrated that the chiefs of Hilly Wancho used to collect three kinds of royal tax which is popularly known as *raja-bheti* in Assamese. In Wancho it is called as *Khud* which is collected once in a year by the chiefs of hilly Wancho. The chiefs of Runu, Rusa, Chopsa villages used to come once in year and stationed in Deopani Naga gaon, Siloni Naga gaon and *Bormedhi's* home for a weeklong to collect that particular tax from the entire Sapekhati, Longpatia, Borhat to Namrup areas upto train tract line.

In this regard, **Mr. Wangshu Wangsu**, a retired government teacher from Chopsa village of Longding district of Arunachal Pradesh asserted that “*there is also another form of Royal tax or raja-bheti that collected by the Naga rajas from the plains peoples during the two occasions were basically i.e. Pongwen and Khamdak*” The former is a kind of community feast program to be organized by the chiefs or the royal family occasionally by seeing the prosperous condition of his people. The chiefs had to be arranged such ceremonies at least thrice in his life. The later ceremony is called *Khamdak*. The *Kham* means log drum which is traditional musical instrument made of bigger sized wood which is often used during festival seasons. During this two special occasions, *tsik-hi-sua* (literally in Wancho, the word *tsik* is referred to a tribal people and *sua* means non-tribal people) the Royal family used to collect a cow or goat in the name of *raja-bheti* from the Plains peoples.

A resident of from Sungi village **Mr Lila Gogoi** of Charaideo district also expressed that *“since the time of Ahom reign, the Hilly Nagas and Plains people had very good-neighborly relations. Every year, every Assamese household had to pay a contribution (Paddy) in the name of raja-bheti. This Raja-bheti system was continuing upto mid 1960’s.”* The Chief of Banfera **Mr Wanglat Wangham** said that *“still the Jaboka and Kanubari tea estate (Companies) use to pay a kind of contribution annually in forms of five quintals of tea and salt to us.”*

In this matter, Mr Padma Wangsu, a resident of Deopani Naga Gaon of Charaideo district also expressed that *“even up to mid 1960s or 70s, this traditional taxation system was existed between Hilly Naga and Plains people through which a strong bond of relationship was also developed between hilly and plains people. However, in colonial time, the land revenue system was changed and such traditional policies were scraped by the then British India government and the modern state boundaries have brought more social gap between hilly and plains peoples.”*

The Present Settlement of Wancho Naga in Assam:

It is seen that after formation of modern state system, the Wancho inhabited areas were divided into various administrative areas. The historical antecedent and settlement of Wancho Naga community living in Assam is as mentioned below.

Village Demographics

Village Name	District	Households	Population
Gariabam Naga Gaon	Dibrugarh	15	100
Khamnua (Paniduria)	Dibrugarh	25	189
Deopani Naga Village	Charaideo	90	600
Baregaon Naga Village	Charaideo	40	260
Hahse-Rusa	Disputed area	130	1000
Kamkuh Rusa	Disputed area	60	500
Tanglam	Disputed area	30	200

Made with Napkin

(Source: Field Study)

In Assam, the Wancho Naga are basically living in four villages namely *Goriabam Naga Gaon* and *Panidoria Naga gaon* under Nahakatia revenue circle of Dibrugarh district and the *Deopani Naga Gaon* and *Baregaon Naga village* under Sapekhati revenue circle of Charaideo district of Assam. As per data given by the Wancho Council of Assam, there are total one hundred and twenty five households in these four villages with approximately two thousand populations. However, above mentioned three villages serial no from 5 to 7 viz. Hahse-Rusa, Kamkuh Rusa and Tanglam villages were under the disputed zone of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh. The border issue and conflict was aroused between the two states from time to time due to lack concrete boundary lines between the states. Before the “Namsai Declaration, 2022”, these three villages as part of Assam, while the Arunachal Pradesh government also claimed entire villages from serial no 4 to 7 as part of its constitutional border area. To settle such boundary dispute and conflict, both the states signed “Namsai Declaration” on July 15, 2022 at Namsai in Arunachal Pradesh wherein 123 villages were minimized to 86 villages. As a part of the declaration, 28 villages including the three villages namely Hahse-Rusa, Kamkuh Rusa and Tanglam that are part of Arunachal Pradesh’s constitutional border would still be included and Assam would retain possession of three villages including the two villages viz. Deopani and Baregaon Naga Gaon for which Arunachal withdrew its claims.

It has been found that they settled in these areas even before the advent of Ahom and resisted against the Ahom while entering their areas. In this matter, **Mr Longshah Wangsu**, a resident of Deopani Naga Gaon under Charaideo district said that *“It was most probably in the last 12th century, while our forefathers were settled in these areas, there were no any other communities and these areas were fully covered with a thick jungle and inhabited by wild animals i.e. tiger, monkey, deer, elephants, reptiles and various species of birds. They cleaned the jungle areas and settled and started agricultural activities. Later on, the outsiders were migrated into these areas along with Britishers and encroached our lands for tea cultivation. Of course, even during the time of Colonial period, our Hilly Wancho rajas used to collect the taxes from those who living in the areas covering upto the present train track line.”*

From this point of view, they are aboriginal tribes of Assam and during the time of Ahom administration, the Wancho Nagas were appointed into various highest portfolios i.e. Barphukan, Naga Pator, Naoboicha etc. Later on, the Modern state system created more border and political complicity and divided into different administrative zone.

The Roots of identity crisis:

It has been found that the like other ethnic groups, the Wancho Naga community are also one of the indigenous tribes of the land of Assam. Despite being an aboriginal tribe of the land, they have been facing ethnic identity crisis due to the combination of various factors including demographic structure, political marginalization, socio-economic vulnerability, neglect by the state policies, geographical and administrative isolation etc. The prime roots or factors responsible for the ethnic identity crisis of Wancho Naga community in Assam are as mentioned below.

Numerical Minority and Demographic Structure:

It has been found that the Wancho Naga community form a micro-ethnic group in Assam dominated and surrounded by larger and more politically assertive groups. There are only four villages with approximately two thousand populations in two different districts like the Charaideo and Dibrugahr districts of Assam. It has been observed that the small population size has made it difficult to assert their identity strongly in comparison to other major tribes and they often fail to secure political seats or leadership positions even in Panchayat elections. It is evident that basically a larger ethnic groups like Bodo, Mishing, Karbi, Dimasa etc. getting more attention through their established autonomous councils, development packages and cultural institutions. But, smaller tribe like the Wancho Naga are often marginalized and neglected even in state's such developmental policies and schemes. Due to their insignificant influence in socio-political landscape of Assam, to some extent they compelled to align with bigger groups for their survival purposes in socio-political scenario. It has often diluted their distinct identity and weakens independent assertion. It has also been observed that feeling of less population as comparison to other tribes has created an internalized inferiority and discouraging the strong assertion of identity.

Geographical and administrative isolation:

It is evident that the Wancho Naga villages like Deopani Naga Gaon and Baregaon Naga Gaon under the Charaideo district of Assam historically settled in the Patkai foothills areas sharing the border with Arunachal Pradesh. It is observed that the due to their geographical location in the borderlands, these areas have often been neglected in terms of infrastructural development and administrative attention in many ways. It has been noticed that their peripheral position between the two states has led to an administrative confusion and overlapping claims which was settled recently as per Namchai Declaration (2022). The Namsai Declaration was signed in 2022 between Assam's Chief Minister Himanta Biswa Sarma and his Arunachal Pradesh counterpart Pema Khandu in order to resolve and reduce the inter-state border dispute affecting 123 villages.

As per the provision of the Declaration, 28 villages that are part of Arunachal Pradesh's constitutional border would be included and Assam would retain possession of the three villages including the Depani and Baregaon Naga Gaon for which Arunachal Pradesh withdrew its claims. It is observed that the Wancho villages in a state of Assam are found marginalization because it is noticed that the developmental schemes are also basically reach to larger or more politically assertive groups which often bypass the micro ethnic groups like Wancho Naga community.

Socio-economic backwardness:

The socio-economic backwardness is one of the prime factors behind the existential crisis of Wancho Nagas of Assam. Due to the lack socio-economic advancement, people are generally deprived off the descent livelihood, security, employment, health, income, housing, education, skills, ethno-cultural preservation etc. The details of socio-economic conditions of the tribe can be easily understood from the below table.

Sectors Composition by Village (2024-25)

Village Name	Primary Sector	Secondary Sector	Tertiary Sector
Deopani Naga Gaon	95%	3%	2%
Baregaon Naga Gaon	96%	2%	2%
Goriabam Naga Gaon	96%	3%	1%
Paniduria Naga Gaon	97%	NA	3%

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The study shows that the overwhelming majority of the households in Wancho Naga inhabited villages such as Deopani Naga Gaon (95%), Baregaon Naga Gaon (96%), Goriabam Naga Gaon (96%) and Paniduria Naga Gaon (97%) are primarily dependent on agriculture and small scale petty business to eke out their livelihood. It has been found that this economic vulnerability has largely limited their capability to invest in education, long term preservation of their cultural practices and activities of community organizations like Wancho Naga council and also reduced bargaining power in political and administrative negotiations. Basically the civil society organizations have been instrumental in mobilizing

or creating consciousness or bringing important issues to the forefront of the public negotiation and also shaping decision of the government. There is lack of active and strong civil society organization like the Wancho Naga Council of Assam which has been formed lately in 2023, but not so actively functioning due various reasons including the financial problems as stated by the President of the council.

Low level of ethnic consciousness and mobilization:

It has been observed that they have lacked of ethnic consciousness due to various factors viz. assimilation with the greater Assamese society and relinquishing their traditional ritual and rites, culture and custom, division of religion, lack of coordination among the community, socio-economic backwardness and lack of active civil societies' organizations to coordinate and mobilize the ethnic consciousness at community level. It is observed that there was no any apex bodies of Wancho Naga community until 2021. The Wancho Council of Assam was formed in 2021 encompassing four villages from Charaideo and Dibrugarh district. However, it has been observed that after formation of the council, it has taken some efforts to resolve the tribe certificate related issues and recognition of the tribe and continually organize the Wancho Oria festival, felicitate the meritorious students and to work for the overall welfare of the community in Assam.

Lack of Institutional Recognition and Support:

It has been observed that in Assam the government has also devised tribe or ethnic group specific policies and schemes in forms of development council, autonomous council, special developmental packages and protective measures for several ethnic groups. However, micro ethnic groups like the Wancho Naga community in Assam have not been granted same institutional safeguards and developmental packages.

In this regard, **Mr Thakwang Wangsu**, a resident of Goriabam Naga Gaon cum former Zila Parishad Member (ZPM) expressed that *“We are micro ethnic group and outnumbered population in Assam, so we can't compete with other advanced and major ethnic groups in any field whether socio-economic, education and political scenario. So, separate institutional and developmental arrangement is highly needed to have a development and empowerment of such disadvantaged section in state”*.

In this matter, **Mr Tingpho Atsaham**, General Secretary of Wancho Naga Council of Assam said that *“we need of special reservation as a most disadvantaged group so that we may get opportunities and privileges in educational and socio-economic development. He also said that though the present BJP led NDA government in both Centre and State government is talking about the Sabka Sath Sabka Vikash, but*

we the micro ethnic tribes of the state facing existential crisis and feel like deprive of the developmental policies of the government.”

4.2.6. Lack of Political Representation:

It has been found that like other ethnic groups of Assam, the Wancho Naga community has been lack of political representation even in local self government. It has been found that in the Panchayat Election held in 2020 only one Ward Member in Gaon Panchayat and one Zila Parishad Member was elected from the Wancho Naga community which was not the same outcome as in the 2025 Panchayat Election. This absence of representation further perpetuates their marginalization in the policy making process and voice their concerns.

In this matter, the General Secretary of the Wancho Naga council, Assam, Mr Wangman Wangsu viewed that *“Due to lack of political representation, our problems and grievance are dealt with properly by the public representations and even our voices are not given due importance by the government. So far, there are only two representatives who have been elected as a Ward Member and Zila Parishad Member in Panchayat election from the Wancho community of Assam in last election.”*

Influence of Dominant Cultures:

The study indicates that modernity and mainstream culture have also significantly impacted the existential crisis of micro-ethnic groups such as the Wancho Naga community of Assam. It has been observed that their traditional way of life including the way of life, food habits, dressing patterns, language and the practice of rituals and rites has undergone dramatic changes under the influence of mainstream culture and modernity. It has been noticed that in the villages of Goriabam and Paniduria under the Dibrugarh district of Assam, they do not speak much their own language and the traditional culture, festivals are no longer properly practiced, as the villagers have fully embraced the Vaishnavite faith.

However, the situation is quite different in Deopani and Baregaon Naga villages of Charaideo district, where the community has adopted Christianity but they widely speak own language in Church services and other community public meetings and occasions. They continue to uses traditional dress code and ornaments and observe festivals and displayed traditional sports occasionally. It has been found that in this regard, the Church has been playing a key role in by promoting educational awareness, encouraging social mobilization and revitalizing the local language. It is observed that in Church services, they speaks in its own language and uses the Holy Bible and hymn songs written in their mother

tongue. It can be argued that such activity of Church has greatly contributed to the preservation of their linguistic identity.

Deprived of Land Rights and Resources:

It is found that the land and resource related issue is one of the major factors behind the identity crisis among them. In each village, many people still deprived of getting land license under ‘Mission Basundhara 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0’. It is also expressed that the traditionally occupied individual and community land and properties are being encroached and purchased by other non-tribal people. Further, it is also found that there is also lack of awareness and mobilization among the people about their constitutional and democratic rights and privileges. It is also reported that most of the time, when they go to the government offices, the government officials doesn’t give importance towards their land registration and in providing land license to them in many ways. Moreover, it is also observed that according to Mr Pangam Wangnow, Gaon Bura of Deopani Naga Gaon *“We the Depani Wancho Naga have been following traditional shifting cultivation in the area covering 450 bighas under Dilli reserved forest which was granted by the then British India government in 1924, but the forest department have made an attempt to evict our cropland and scraped the privileges many times which is our right and the land is not yet recognized under forest rights act, 2006. But we are still fighting and will never let it go this privilege from our hand which is our ancestral land enjoying by us since time immemorial.”*

Community Organization: Approaches, Strategies and Functions

It can be argued that the proactive role of community-based organizations is vital for strong ethnic identity assertion of any community. In the context of Wancho Naga tribe of Assam, the tribe constitutes a smaller population with relatively weak organizational structures and their ethnic-based issues and challenges are often ignored and neglected in the broader socio-political landscape of the state. Of course, despite such challenges, the community organizations are taking efforts to preserve and assert their identities. Basically, the organizational structure of the Naga communities in Assam is broadly functions at three tiers such as village-level committees or councils, community or tribe-level organizations or councils and state-level community organizations as mentioned below.

Village Council or Committee:

At the grassroots, the village committees or councils primarily address matters concerning the village and its immediate welfare. It has been found that in case of the Wancho Naga community in Assam, there are active village level committees in Deopani and Baregan Naga Gaon under the

Charaideo district of Assam. The village councils and its composition and functioning is based on democratic system from election or selection of officials, adoption of resolutions in annual general meeting for governing the village affairs, accounting and auditing the finance and fund etc. The village councils have largely focuses on preserving the identity, culture and tradition of the community, resolving the petty domestic issues through negation and meeting, organizing festivals, extension activities like plantations, occasionally cleaning the village area. It has been found that the village councils have also organized sports tournaments, anti drugs campaign, medical health camps and initiated for charitable works and community welfare activities etc.

Tribe Specific Council:

It has been found that the Wancho Naga Council (Assam) is the tribe specific body of the indigenous Wancho Naga community of Assam. It was formed in 2022 under the leadership of Mr Shompha Wangus, Mr Wangman Wangsu and Mr Tingpho Atsaham encompassing four village councils or committees from Charaideo and Dibrugarh districts of Assam. The main purpose of this umbrella body is to represent the community collectively, raise their voice for common causes and assert their rights who have been historically residing in Assam since time immemorial. The main purpose of the council is as mentioned below.

- To preserve and promote traditional culture, language and festivals through awareness programs and publications.
- To mobilize youth and students to participate in cultural and developmental activities.
- To interact with government and policy-makers to highlight their developmental needs such as education, infrastructure, land and resource and employment opportunities.
- To build a relationship with other ethnic organizations thereby strengthening bonding, belongingness and shared identity.
- To take effort or facilitate skill development and livelihood programs so that the community can adapt to modern changes without losing their cultural roots.
- To promote inter-community harmony and dialogue thereby ensuring recognition of their unique identity in multicultural society of the state.

It is believed that these efforts, if continued and strengthened, the organization will able to contribute significantly towards the ethnic assertion, socio-political recognition and cultural survival of the Wancho Naga community in Assam. It has been observed that the organization has taken some efforts like organizing felicitation program for students and youths for their achievements in various fields,

organized Oria festivals centrally and raised the voice against the discrimination and injustice against the community at different point of times. Under the aegis of Wancho Naga Council, Assam and other tribal organizations has jointly submitted a memorandum to the government in 2023 to resolve the issue of not granting the Scheduled Tribe (H) certificate for the time being and demanded to recognize and mention them as a permanent tribe of the district in the certificate.

As a result, the government has taken their demand seriously and continued to issue the certificate for the people of the community. It has been found that the organization tries to build good and harmonious relations with the other communities and establish their strong existence and recognition in the larger Assam society.

State Level Naga Body:

At the apex level, the All Assam Naga Welfare Society (AANWS) serves as the umbrella body encompassing all the indigenous Naga tribes of Assam. It was established in 2021 with the collective consent of eight indigenous Naga tribal councils such as Rengma, Ao, Wancho, Konyak, Nokte, Sema, Tangsa, Rongmei Naga. It has been observed that the AANWS has active members from the Wancho Naga community who have actively participated in various activities and extended all kinds of support towards the successful functioning of the organization. It is observed that the AANWS has raised voice against the issues and problems facing by the entire Naga communities of Assam including the Wancho Naga such as the issue of land rights and recognition of revenue village, eviction policies of the government, imposing government projects on the Naga inhabited etc.

It has also been noticed that under the collaborative efforts of All Assam Naga Welfare Society (AANWS) and all tribe specific councils has introduced a new dimension in Naga ethnic assertion in Assam. Its main aim is to safeguard the collective interests of the Naga communities living in Assam since time immemorial by raising a unified voice, articulating shared interest and pursuing common goals and visions for socio-political recognition and development.

Policy implications:

- It is seen that the Constitution have provided equal rights and opportunities for each and every persons and communities to protect their distinct identity, culture, language, customary practices as well as special provisions for Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes to promote their socio-economic, educational, cultural, political and ethnic interest. Despite such measures, micro ethnic groups are facing existential crisis due to violent ethnic clashes, over domination by the majority tribes and lack

of adequate political representation etc. In this regard, the issue on representation needs to be seriously reconsidered for the empowerment of such disadvantaged tribal communities like Wancho Naga of Assam. They need to be recognized as tribe not only for the purpose of giving education, employment and economic benefits but also for the political representation.

- The government should take steps and sanction adequate funds to preserve and promote language, art, tradition and cultural practice of all tribal groups including Wancho Naga community living in Assam.
- The government should take effective steps to eradicate the problem of socio-economic marginalization i.e. poverty, lack of access quality education, employment as experienced by such disadvantaged section of the society. They need to be provided special reservations for job and admission into educational institutes on the grounds of most disadvantaged micro ethnic groups of Assam.
- The students, youths and womens' organizations and the Wancho Council of Assam needs to play an active role in case of organizing and mobilizing the ethnic identity consciousness among the people level by organizing various awareness programs from time to time.
- The government requires a multifaceted approaches and strategies to sort out the ethnic conflict situation and identity issues i.e. power-sharing, adequate financial and institutional accommodation, inclusive and comprehensive policies and schemes for overall socio-economic, cultural and political elevation of the communities.

Conclusion:

From above study it is understood that many ethnic groups including Wancho Naga community are facing challenges of identity preservation, representation and survival in a socio-political landscape of the state which is often dominated by larger communities. It has been found that the Wancho Naga group with smaller population strength are facing challenges in strongly assert their distinct ethnic identity. Despite this difficulty, they continue to preserve their unique identity and heritage through cultural practices, oral traditions and participation in wider platforms such as the All Assam Naga Welfare Society (AANWS) which has allowed them to extend their voice and align with other Naga tribes for collective interest in the socio-political landscape of Assam.

It can be argued that understanding the issue of identity among micro-ethnic groups like Wancho Naga community has broader implications. Because, in state policy making process and academic research, the issues and challenges of smaller tribe are often unnoticed and ignored due to lack of limelight the discourse and insignificant political influences. It can be argued that for the Wancho Naga,

ethnic identity assertion is not only about cultural survival but also about access to rights, resources and political recognition within the diverse ethnic mosaic in Assam. In this regard, there is need of ensuring their participation in local governance, socio-economic programs and educational opportunities is vital for empowering the community and preventing them further marginalization in the days to come. It may be noted that the government has taken various accommodative measures to address the underlying issues of ethnic minorities in the state. But, so far, no such imperative measures have been taken against such micro ethnic groups like Wancho community of Assam. It is high time for all stakeholders and policy makers to lay emphasis on the comprehensive and inclusive developmental policies and strategies and to make society progressive, prospective and inclusive one.

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